

Quantum Mechanics and Pressure Balance in the Presence of Flux and Momentum Discontinuity

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One may consider constant fluxes which exist for all x points in space. These are associated with a constant velocity and a momentum. Consider next a discontinuity which does not change energy. For example, one may have energy E , momentum p and a constant potential V_1 which suddenly changes to V_2 at $x=x_0$ with E remaining constant. This leads to a momentum discontinuity as well as a flux discontinuity, but no work is done. As a result, there exists a pressure balance (related to an incident flux, a reflected one and the new p_2 flux for $x>x_0$), i.e. there is no discontinuity in pressure. A single constant flux also has no discontinuity in pressure either. We suggest there should exist a continuous function of momentum and x which allows for/ensures this pressure continuity. The momentum discontinuity may be at any x_0 , but the pressure balance is the same. As a result, one would expect this function and its first derivative to be continuous at x_0 , but a combination of the two should eliminate the function (of p and x_0) leaving only a pressure balance equation. In other words, two equations need to combine to create a single classical pressure balance equation, suggesting that there may exist a square root flux type probability function.

We suggest that pressure balance at momentum discontinuity points (with E remaining constant) may be the only consideration necessary to ultimately obtain the quantum free particle $\exp(ipx)$. An advantage of this pressure-only viewpoint is that it accounts for weighted averages of $\exp(ipx)$ having the same form, namely $\exp(ip_{\text{ave}}(\text{rms}) x)$ and $\exp(-ip_{\text{ave}}(\text{rms}) x)$ in a potential with infinite walls. Pressure considerations may be applied to a single particle $\exp(ipx)$ or an ensemble, yielding the same form if the same conditions apply. We argue that both a square well potential and infinite well potential are examples of momentum discontinuities, except in this case one has discontinuities in ensemble values (i.e. average values).

Free Particle

A free particle with constant velocity and momentum may be described by constant flux everywhere in space. Furthermore, there is constant pressure at each x point. For the sake of argument, one might suggest there exists a function $F(p,x)$ linked with flux which is continuous together with its first derivative. A combination of the two should then yield pressure i.e.

$$AF(px) \text{ and } A \frac{dF}{dx} \rightarrow \text{Pressure} = (\text{flux})p \quad ((1))$$

$$((1)) \text{ suggests that } \frac{dF}{dx} = p G(px) \text{ and so } \text{Pressure} = p A F(p,x)G(p,x)$$

$F(p,x)G(p,x)$, however, should be a constant B such that $AB=\text{flux}$ i.e. $F \frac{dF}{dx} = \text{Constant}$ which is nonzero. This suggests $F(px)$ cannot be real, except for \sqrt{x} which grows with x , but should be $A\exp(ipx)$ to stop the growth. ((2)) In such a case, one multiplies AF^* with $A\frac{dF}{dx}$.

Here we use p and not $2p$ in the pressure calculator because the particle is not reflecting. The above is a suggestion which probably would not be taken seriously unless there were compelling experimental evidence. We argue next, however, that discontinuities in momentum at sharp x points lend more support for ((2))

Momentum, Flux Discontinuities at x_0

It is possible to have momentum and flux discontinuities at a point x_0 with energy remaining constant. A specific example is to have an energy E , p and constant potential V_1 for $x < x_0$ and $E, p_2, V_2 = a$ different constant for $x \geq x_0$. We argue that because E remains constant, no work is done, yet given the presence of momenta and fluxes there should be a pressure balance at x_0 , x_0 may take on any value. In other words, whether the particle is free (above section) or encountering a momentum discontinuity at x_0 , pressure balance is maintained and it appears there may be a function $F(p, x)$ associated with this balance. This function would then be continuous together with its first derivative at x_0 . The two equations would somehow combine to remove the presence of x_0 and yield a pressure balance. We consider $AF(p, x) + BF(-p, x)$ for $x < x_0$ and $CF(p_2, x)$ for $x \geq x_0$. Then:

$$AF(p, x) + BF(-p, x) = CF(p_2, x) \text{ at } x = x_0 \quad ((3a)) \text{ and}$$

$$pAF(p, x) - pBF(-p, x) = p_2CF(p_2, x) \text{ at } x = x_0 \quad ((3b))$$

The first derivative ((3b)) ensures a difference of squares form due to p and the reflected $-p$. From the section above for the free particle, one sees that if $F(p, x) = \exp(ipx)$, one may take the complex conjugate of ((3a)) and multiply it by ((3b)) to obtain a pressure balance equation if AA, BB and CC are considered to be fluxes i.e.

$$pAA - pBB = p_2 CC \text{ at any } x_0 \quad ((4))$$

Thus, an unusual $\exp(ipx)$ function, which exists in all of space, emerges in order to ensure pressure balance both in free space and at discontinuity points. The implications of $\exp(ipx)$ are large in that it suggests a characteristic length constant/ p associated with each p value. Such a characteristic p linked length does not appear in classical mechanics. We note that pressure balance ((4)), which is a classical type of equation, is associated with $\exp(ipx)$ which acts as a kind of square root flux which ultimately ensures the balance. The square root flux form emerges because one requires both continuity of the functions $F(px)$ and their first derivative. In other words, two conditions are required to create a single balance equation ((4)).

The reason for having a function of x in the first place is that one wishes to ensure pressure balance for a free particle as well as one which may encounter discontinuities at any x_0 . In other words, the pressure balance is not somehow created at the discontinuity point by itself, but is associated with $\exp(ipx)$. Given that $\exp(ipx)$ exists at all x points, it does not travel with the particle. Furthermore, because it is directly linked to pressure, it only contains p (momentum) and not velocity. In other words, $\exp(ipx)$ seems to be associated with a kind of square root flux probabilistic picture of a problem.

Pressure and the Question of Averages

We have argued above that a square root flux type probability $A \exp(ipx)$ emerges in order to ensure pressure balance for a single particle. In such a case, p has a clear definition, namely the momentum of the single particle. We ask: What if one had a sum of $\exp(ipx)$'s? If $\exp(ipx)$ is a kind of probability, then OR situations might lead to summations. This would then suggest an rms average momentum and average flux which should still lead to pressure balance considerations. In other words, if pressure balance in space is the key feature of quantum mechanics, one may see the $\exp(ipx)$ form as well as an $\exp(ip_{\text{ave}}(rms) x)$ form. In particular, if one considers an infinite square well potential, one has free space between the walls and from the above arguments would consider the forms:

$$A \exp(ip_{\text{ave}}(rms) x) \text{ and } A \exp(-i p_{\text{ave}}(rms) x) \quad ((5))$$

In particular, a solution of $C \sin(p_{\text{rms}} x)$ within the well, such that it is 0 at the well walls is associated with an average kinetic energy of:

$$p_{\text{rms}}^2 / 2m \text{ (nonrelativistic)} \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{Average pressure using } \exp(ipx) \text{ as a probability is: } p_{\text{rms}} \cos(p_{\text{rms}} x) / \sin(p_{\text{rms}} x) \quad ((7))$$

To deal with the average pressure at the walls, one may multiply by density $C \sin(p_{\text{rms}} x) \sin(p_{\text{rms}} x)$ which yields 0 at both walls. $\exp(ip_{\text{rms}} x)$, however, is not 0 at the walls and may be used in a discontinuity equation based on a kind of pressure balance at a wall i.e.

$$A \exp(ip_{\text{rms}} x) + B \exp(-ip_{\text{rms}} x) = 0 \text{ at } x = x_{\text{wall}} \quad A = B \quad ((8))$$

((8) is the same type of discontinuity equation used for a single particle momentum discontinuity. This explains why the same single particle $\exp(ipx)$ form emerges, albeit with a different p , namely p_{rms} .

We suggest that the interaction at the wall is exactly like the momentum discontinuity described above, except that one does not have a single momentum, but an rms average. Why is an rms average momentum required? Consider the more general case of an arbitrary $V(x)$ which may allow for bound states. $V(x)$, with constant E (energy) at each x , implies that $KE(x)$, but $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with a constant p and so constant kinetic energy. One requires an ensemble $W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$ to create a $KE_{\text{ave}}(x)$. This also implies an average p , as well as an rms one. We suggest that the same ideas should hold for the infinite well potential. We further note that there is no $\exp(ipx)$ outside the walls, but in the single particle discontinuity picture above, there were $\exp(ipx)$ forms everywhere in space. We suggest that there must be a linear combination of $\exp(ipx)$ s outside the walls which yields $W(x) = 0$ outside the walls and a $\sin(p_{\text{ave}} x)$ type solution inside. In other words, one may analyze this problem in terms of $\exp(ip_{\text{ave}}(rms) x)$ and $\exp(-ip_{\text{ave}}(rms) x)$, but at the same time there are

$\exp(ipx)$ s which, when weighted, add to create $\exp(ip_{\text{ave}}(\text{rms}) x)$ and $\exp(-ip_{\text{ave}}(\text{rms}) x)$. Given that one bases everything on pressure balance, pressure is not concerned with a single particle p or a $p_{\text{ave}}(\text{rms})$.

A square well potential which is not infinite is another example of such a discontinuity which uses averages and balances $W(x)$ and its first derivative at the walls of the potential.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that the form $A\exp(ipx)$ ensures a pressure balance in space. It is particularly useful in establishing this balance at momentum discontinuities in space in situations for which E is constant i.e. a constant V_1 potential for $x < x_0$ and a different constant V_2 for $x \geq x_0$. Because $A\exp(ipx)$ and its first derivative must be continuous at any x_0 , one deals with a kind of square root flux probability. In fact, the form $\exp(ipx)$ emerges from assuming a function $A F(p, x)$ which, together with its first derivative, is continuous at any x_0 , but which may be combined to eliminate x_0 and yield a pressure balance equation. In other words, a single classical pressure balance equation requires two combined continuity equations, leading to the notion of a square root flux probability creating classical observables like pressure balance.

We argue that pressure balance seems to be the main driver for $\exp(ipx)$ and note that pressure may be associated with a single momentum p or with an rms average. This leads to $\exp(ip_{\text{ave}}(\text{rms}) x)$ and $\exp(-ip_{\text{ave}}(\text{rms}) x)$ solutions for a square well potential. One has the same kind of momentum discontinuity at the well walls and may establish a function which is continuous together with its first derivative. This function, called a wavefunction, however, is also a weighted sum of $\exp(ipx)$ s (single particle $\exp(ipx)$ s).

In other words, for an infinite well potential, $C \sin(p_{\text{ave}}(\text{rms}) x)$ may be obtained directly from a discontinuity equation at the infinite well walls assuming that there is no probability or p_{rms} outside the wall. This calculation is of the identical form as a single particle discontinuity one. At the same time, one may create a weighted average of $\exp(ipx)$ s to find a function which is zero outside the walls and goes to zero inside the walls at the wall boundaries. The two solutions are the same. The discontinuity approach is simpler because it is based on the same calculation as single particle momentum discontinuity. Thus pressure arguments may be used to find various quantum solutions in momentum discontinuity situations.